

THE INFLUENCE OF MASS MEDIA IN THE RISE AND CHANGE OF CULTURE

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Abstract: Mass media is one of the most significant agents of cultural change and it has now become an essential part of human society. Consequently, through its multifaceted channels occasioned by the technological revolution, it is now seen as influencing what people think and how to think about. Furthermore, it has redefined cultural ideologies and perceptions. Using McLuhan's and Cultural Imperialism's perspective to theoretically underpin it, this chapter thus traces how mass media has influenced cultural change in Africa by showing examples specific from Kenya. From this it is clear that mass media is rapidly changing the cultures of virtually all aspects of Kenyan society whenever it has come in contact with mass media. The chapter then concludes that Kenyan society is an example of African society experiencing the second phase of colonization through the mass media.

Keywords: *mass media, culture change, technological revolution, African cultures.*

Today, the stakes are higher. Technology has greatly influenced the media activities. It has increased the speed and accessibility of information. The myriad mutations of social media play a controversial role in society. People were used to sharing their common interests in radio or TV characters and major news stories in the back yard, bar room, and coffee shop conversations, but the proliferation of specialized publications and personalized channels has fragmented the media

audience. Many citizens have become critical of the lack of quality in so much contemporary culture and are concerned about the overwhelming amount of information now available.

Even the computer, once indicated as an educational salvation of children, has created confusion. Today, when kids announce that they are on the computer', parents may wonder whether they are writing a term paper, playing a video game, talking to cyber space strangers, shopping for sneakers or peeking at pornography. (Campbell et al, 2007).

The mass media in Africa has played a key role in promoting social development, through public enlightenment and sensitization and its performance has gone beyond earlier expectations. Currently, communities in general and individuals in particular are bombarded constantly with messages from a multitude of sources which include the TV, billboards, newspapers, magazines, and social media to name but a few. These messages promote not only products, but moods, attitudes, and a sense of what is and/or is not important.

The argument here is that the culture of everyday life in Africa has become intertwined with the media to the extent that African culture has been diluted by westernization. Although the African has been freed from colonialism, Africans are not ready to embrace freedom to the extent of wholly appreciating their culture. When Africa was colonized, they were made to believe that their culture is primitive and backward. To appear civilized, Africans started adopting the western culture dropping most of the African values and norms. And through the media, the western cultural values are being passed on and emulated in Africa. This implies that the developed countries still influence the behaviour of the developing countries.

Cultural Imperialism Theory further argues that humans do not have free will to choose how they feel, act, think, and live and this is echoed by the Agenda Setting Theory. These two theories agree that people react to what they see or hear on media because there is nothing else to compare it to besides their own lives, which

is usually portrayed as less than what it should be. In addition, the media will play a major part in changing the behaviour since the audience lacks the capacity to filter information they consume.

More often than not, when we listen or watch both Kenyan and international media, it is difficult to discern the differences in their agenda. In other words, there is an uncanny similarity in most items. For example, when not discussing politics, it is crime stories that take the centre stage. What this tells us is that the media has made everybody in the world to think in a certain way as stated Agenda Setting Theory (McCombs and Shaw 1972). Moreover, the media has tended to portray the western culture as high culture while African Culture is seen as the low culture or popular culture. And this is not the case with Kenya alone but with all developing countries.

Furthermore, Cultural Imperialism Theory states that western nations dominate the media around the world which in return has a powerful effect on the cultures of developing countries like Kenya through the imposition of western viewpoints which in turn gradually erode native cultures (Schiller, 1973). These viewpoints are manifested in the movies that we watch, such as the Mexican soap operas, which have become common in Kenya hence influencing the dating patterns, dress code and values that influence relationships. The recent move by local TV channels to introduce singing competitions and reality shows can be related to ideas borrowed from the western media that runs reality shows which may not be in consonance with mainstream Kenyan culture but just because it is foreign, then it is considered superior. (For instance, the formats of these competitions bear an uncanny resemblance to “America’s Got Talent, Britain’s Got Talent, and Big Brother reality shows).

In addition, the theory points out that because of the economic muscle which enables them to do so, Western Civilization produces the majority of the media (film, news, comics, and so on). Consequently, the rest of the world purchases those productions because it is cheaper for them to do so rather than produce their

own. Thus, developing countries are watching media filled with the Western world's ways of living, believing, and thinking. The developing world cultures then start to want and do the same things in their countries and thus erode their own culture.

Mushi (1966: 13) notes that, "one could hardly visualize the existence of a nation without culture or, if such a nation were to exist it would merely be a disunited group of people living together simply because there existed geographical boundaries and some political authority to control them from above." (Quoted in Fortner, 1993).

At the onset of colonization, European colonialists created many of the present African countries by imposing arbitrary geographical boundaries. After independence, the consequence of these t was often severe difficulty in building potent political institutions, implementing sound economic development projects, and developing relevant national cultural policies, because tribal animosities, linguistic differences, and socio-cultural dynamics that interfered with these processes (Schiller, 1973).

As stated in Fortner 1993, one cultural manifesto adopted in Africa acknowledged that, "culture starts with the people as creators of themselves and transformers of their environment. Culture, in its widest and most complete sense, enables men (sic) to give shape to their lives" (quoted in Dumila, 1976, p. 2). The leaders of developing countries, however, had difficulty seeing how culture, in the sense outlined by this manifesto, could develop in nations swamped with Western cultural imports: films, television programs, music, newspapers, and magazines.

To confound this, the Western industrial powers, especially the United States have dominated the production and distribution channels for media materials; cultural materials that have become increasingly popular worldwide. For example, most people talk about *Hollywood* when it comes to features films and television programmes yet we have *Nollywood* from Nigeria. Furthermore, other than South Africa which tries to promote local music, the major source of music for the youth

today in Kenya is MTV, the Music TV channel from the United States. As a result, the youth have sometimes adapted delinquent behaviour from such sites as they try to ape their favorite celebrities who most of the times come from different social settings. This has changed the norms and values of various developing countries like Kenya. It is also clear that 80 percent of the magazines on the streets of Nairobi are from the Western world and a similar percentage of the information in the internet is from developed countries. On the other hand, the flow of information from developing countries to the developed is minimal.

The effects of the above brings us to the conclusion that, through the mass media and communication technologies, Western and other developed countries' cultures have infiltrated the African cultural context to the extent that, for instance, most Kenyan have given up their traditional dressing codes to embrace foreign modes of dressing. The advertisements on TV and the internet impose western values on the Kenyan audience. . For example, beauty products like *Nivea* are advertised by models who push for the western idea of beauty. The models are skinny, light skinned and tall as opposed to the African concept of a beautiful woman who is dark, of medium height, even short and plump in some cultures. The consequence of this is that today women in Kenya go to great lengths to starve themselves to be slim or bleach themselves with dangerous chemicals to have a lighter skin.

The flow of hegemonic information from the West has also had a significant impact on religious identity for Kenyans. Today, African traditional religions have been largely abandoned and a majority of Kenyans profess Christianity in a myriad of forms (denominations). This is not just because of the effects of earlier European missionaries who came to Africa and convinced natives to abandon their traditional religions claiming it was barbaric and devilish. Today's Christian adherents, particularly of the Pentecostal and evangelical persuasion can be attributed to media influence through various religious channels domiciled most in the West. For example, TBN, a gospel media channel in the US can broadcast all

over the world via satellite and Kenya's Family Media is a product of TBN, indicating that religious channels can also wire their materials that advocate the western religious viewpoints to affiliated local religious channels. Moreover, anyone doing shopping in the capital city of Kenya can see the Kenyan religious market is filled with books, CDs, magazines and gospel music from the West.

Although mass media is acknowledged for its positive impact, it is also blamed for what is being seen as cultural imperialism. The major aspect of cultural imperialism is the information flow issue. As with international news flow, developing countries have often criticized Western industrialized states, particularly the United States, for their domination of media cultural products and the implications of that dominance for their own cultural values.

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